

Ethyne functionalized meso-phenothiazinyl-phenyl-porphyrins: synthesis and optical properties of free base versus protonated species.

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Table of contents:

NMR spectra of compounds **2a**, **2b**, **2e**, **2f**, **2i**

HRMS spectra of compounds **2b**, **2e**, **2f**, **2j**

Figure S2. ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of compound **2a** (CDCl_3 , 150 MHz)

Figure S3. (^1H - ^1H) COSY spectrum of compound **2a** (aromatic part, CDCl_3)

Figure S4. (^1H - ^{13}C) HMQC spectrum of compound **2a** (aromatic part, CDCl_3)

Figure S5. ^1H -NMR spectrum of compound **2b** (CDCl_3 , 600 MHz)

Figure S6. ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of compound **2b** (CDCl_3 , 150 MHz)

Figure S7. ^1H -NMR spectrum of compound **2e** (CDCl_3 , 600 MHz)

Figure S8. ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of compound **2e** (CDCl₃, 150 MHz)

Figure S9. ^1H -NMR spectrum of compound **2f** (CDCl₃, 600 MHz)

Figure S10. ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of compound **2f** (CDCl_3 , 150 MHz)

Figure S11. (^1H - ^1H) COSY spectrum of compound **2f** (aromatic part, CDCl_3)

Figure S12. (^1H - ^{13}C) HMQC spectrum of compound **2f** (aromatic part, CDCl_3)

Figure S13. ^1H -NMR spectrum of compound **2i** (CDCl_3 , 600 MHz)

Figure S14. ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of compound **2i** (CDCl_3 , 150 MHz)

Figure S15. HRMS (APCI+) spectrum of compound **2b**

Figure S16. HRMS (APCI+) spectrum of compound **2e**

Figure S17. HRMS (APCI+) spectrum of compound **2f**

Figure S18. HRMS (APCI+) spectrum of compound **2j**